

FEATURES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CLINICAL THINKING OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Annotation.

Modern education of medical university students requires a lot of attention to the presentation of the theory of medical diagnostic thinking. It is impossible to teach a student only the methods of studying a patient, it is impossible to make him remember those symptoms and syndromes that correspond only to a particular disease. He needs to be trained to properly use the results of his methodical work and consciously conduct the process of clinical thinking. Practical actions on volunteers or on dummies, rather than on patients, improve the possibility of initial skill acquisition in the full and consistent development of each stage, then give the opportunity to practice / train until competence is achieved (automatism and high quality of execution). And only when competence is achieved, the application of clinical and practical skills on patients is more interesting for students, since they understand and successfully perform all stages of the examination.

Key words.

clinical thinking, practical skills, systematized stages, competence.

The process of forming a highly professional specialist begins at the early stages of training at a medical university [1,7]. Creating a professional, including in the field of family medicine, in a relatively short period of time to gain knowledge in a medical university is a responsible and super-complex task.

In the conditions of a rapidly increasing flow of information, advanced technologies and teaching methods, higher educational institutions have a serious

problem: in the short time allowed for the educational process, they have time to teach students most of the knowledge, skills and abilities that advanced science offers. At the same time, not forgetting about the upbringing of a highly educated person and a worthy member of society.

The traditional model of learning (unilateral receipt of information and its automatic memorization) is not justified today and has proved its inconsistency neither in time nor in the quality of its perception.

In this connection, over the last decades of training, we strive to ensure that the student ceases to be a passive recipient of information, on the contrary, he should be an active participant in the educational process. Be able to extract new information, systematize, analyze and select the most relevant, the most necessary. In addition, he must be able to return to the information received at the right moment, think clinically and develop his own point of view. As a result of this approach, a specialist is formed who is ready to timely identify and solve the problems of the population comprehensively at a qualitatively new level. It should be noted that the clinical competence of a future specialist depends not only on how and what information the student has learned, but also on its application in practice. The student should be able to build interpersonal communication with patients. Without confidential conversations, neither diagnosis, nor treatment, nor prevention is possible. Effective face-to-face communication allows the doctor to solve a number of tasks: to strengthen trusting relationships, to obtain the data necessary to establish a diagnosis, to quickly and accurately carry out diagnostic measures and develop a treatment plan, to inform the patient of the necessary information, to convince him to give up bad habits and lead a healthy lifestyle. Taking responsibility for the patient is achieved by systematically honing practical skills, the ability to think clinically and the ability to diagnose.

To date, the process of studying at a higher educational institution allows you to get a specialist capable of independent search for information and ready to work in a medical institution, which is impossible without clinical thinking [2]. Clinical thinking is a meaningfully specified process of dialectical thinking that gives integrity and completeness to medical knowledge [10]. In the process of diagnosis in medicine, non-specific symptoms and syndromes are discussed. This means that in clinical medicine there are no symptoms that would be a sign of only one disease. Any symptom may or may not be present in a patient with a certain disease. Ultimately, this explains why the clinical diagnosis is always more or less a hypothesis, as S.P. Botkin pointed out at the time [3]. A medical diagnosis can be

accurate only with respect to those criteria that are currently accepted by the scientific community [10].

Clinical medicine became known as clinical medicine from Burgava [9]. Its defining feature is that clinical thinking is brought up in the process of communication between a student, a teaching doctor and a patient at his bedside. This explains why any kind of distance learning in medicine is unacceptable. Neither a trained volunteer, nor a phantom, nor role-playing games, nor theoretical mastering of the subject can replace the patient.

It is impossible to consider the specifics of clinical thinking in isolation from taking into account the style of clinical thinking of its development and changes in the near future. Style is a feature of the method, depending on the epoch [10]. In ancient medicine, the main thing in diagnosis was to determine the prognosis of diseases. By the end of the XIX century, a doctor's style of work had developed, consisting in observing patients, examining him according to the traditional model: first questioning, then objective examination and then laboratory and instrumental examination.

The advanced information and pedagogical technologies used today, the latest technical means and training resources are aimed at comprehensive intellectual, physical and psychological preparation of the student for the work of a doctor.

According to the above, in recent years, a variety of modern technologies have been widely used in the implementation of the educational process at the Tashkent Medical Academy, which make it possible to increase the effectiveness of teaching graduate students [4]. In particular, innovations in modeling the stages of patient counseling in family polyclinics [5].

An important role in modeling patient counseling in family polyclinics is assigned to the formation and development of clinical thinking in the future doctor [4]. The solution of this problem is hardly possible only by transferring knowledge from a teacher to a student, since clinical thinking cannot be learned from textbooks and manuals, no matter how well they are compiled. This requires practice under the guidance of a mentor/experienced teacher. Botkin S.P. and Zakharin G.A. also attached crucial importance to the assimilation of the method of clinical examination in the preparation of future doctors. So, Botkin said: "If the student has mastered the clinical method of counseling, he is quite ready for independent activity." In modern textbooks, the question of clinical thinking is almost nowhere considered. Even such a major clinician as M.P. Konchalovsky, arguing that "a doctor ... must learn to reason, think logically, or, as they say, master clinical thinking," does not indicate where and how a future specialist should learn this.

So, where and how should clinical thinking be educated? In our opinion, for students of the medical and medical pedagogical faculty, this should happen during training at all clinical departments and in training modules, primarily in clinics of internal and surgical diseases, which form the basis of medical education of a doctor of any specialty. In these clinics, the patient's disease can be disassembled and analyzed in its entirety, therefore, it is in these clinics that the analysis of patients can serve as the basis for the development of clinical thinking. The formation of students' skills in the diagnosis of therapeutic and surgical profile in its typical course with the justification of treatment, rehabilitation issues and preventive measures, as well as knowledge of modern principles of emergency medical care in conditions of the most common diseases of internal organs is the goal of these disciplines.

As mentioned above, the leading role in the learning process is given to mastering the stages of receiving patients / volunteers and providing them with medical care against the background of increasing the responsibility of teachers for developing independent work skills, for stimulating the professional growth of students, fostering their creative activity and initiative. The last two components of education are formed precisely in the process of students' work in training modules. In this regard, it should be recognized that modeling the solution of patients'/volunteers' problems is not just an important form of the educational process, but should become its basis. Since the student needs to be transferred from a passive consumer of knowledge to an active creator of knowledge, who is able to formulate a problem, analyze ways to solve it, find the optimal result and prove its correctness.

So, graduate students, in practical classes in modules, are trained to simulate the admission of patients in outpatient settings according to the established situational task. By consulting a patient/volunteer using the stages of solving problems of the population, future specialists acquire the skills of constructive, integrating and logical thinking. In addition, by repeatedly practicing the skills of receiving patients / volunteers, they improve and hone their knowledge gained in previous courses. The purpose and evaluation of this type of training is not so much the diagnosis (although this is also very important), but how the student came to this diagnosis and what practical tactics of the family doctor he applied.

Learning the ability to question; the ability to identify risk factors and problems of patients; to demonstrate a syndromic objective examination; to establish the main and concomitant diagnosis; to make a personal plan of laboratory and instrumental studies aimed not at the disease, but at the patient; to

determine the categories of medical care services; to prescribe the correct non-drug and, proven effectiveness, drug treatment; to determine and conduct preventive measures; to carry out effective dynamic monitoring of patients subject to medical examination, students acquire professional skills corresponding to the qualification characteristics of a family doctor. But this is not the main goal either.

The main purpose of this type of training is the formation and development of clinical thinking in a future doctor. This is a professional, creative solution to the issues of diagnosis, treatment and determination of the prognosis of the disease in a particular patient based on knowledge, experience, competencies and medical intuition. The patient cannot be replaced by a trained volunteer, a phantom, a simulator, role-playing games, or theoretical mastery of the subject. Clinical thinking is brought up in the process of communication between the student, the teacher and the patient at his bedside. It, together with constructive, integrating and the ability to collect a good medical history, is an element of medical art. Despite the fact that a person's thinking is one, it is formed exclusively individually for everyone.

It is important to know that by mastering medicine outside of communication with the patient and the teacher, students will place accents of significance in their own way in the studied subject. This means that students' thinking will not be clinical. Therefore, solving the problems of patients /volunteers according to the stages of modeling clinical examination, and acquiring good counseling skills, students need to apply them to real patients under the supervision of an experienced teacher who not only observes, but also evaluates the clinical and practical actions of students. Students should see, hear and feel patients in the appropriate clinics and in the conditions of a family polyclinic. Where the diagnosis with the greatest accuracy, the appointment of the correct treatment and the choice of management tactics is the main goal of teaching at the bedside. Such conditions predispose to the development of the following elements of clinical thinking: understanding the identified symptoms; hypothesizing about the desired disease; a chain of reasoning that leads the doctor to a diagnostic conclusion; mental reproduction of a possible sequence of factors and situations forming the etiology and pathogenesis of the disease; preparation of a medical prognosis; preparation of a treatment plan; evaluation of the results of examination and treatment; planning of preventive and rehabilitation measures.

SYSTEMATIZED STAGES OF LEARNING PRACTICAL SKILLS

No	Stage	Content of practical actions
1	Skill Acquisition	The student tries to learn all the stages of performing the required practical skill, but needs the help of a teacher / mentor.
2	Competence of the skill	The student has mastered all the stages and, under the supervision of a teacher/mentor, can independently perform the required practical skill.
3	Skill proficiency	The student has mastered all the stages and successfully performs the required practical skill first on the volunteer/dummy, and then on the patient.
4	Analysis of the results obtained	The student has a competent analysis of the data obtained, result of a clinical or practical skill performed (in some cases the help of a teacher / mentor).
5	Tactics of a family doctor	Using the results obtained, the student has the ability to fully determine the necessary category of medical care services according to the qualification characteristics of a family doctor.

In our opinion, practical actions on volunteers or on dummies, and not on patients, improve the possibility of initial skill acquisition in the full and consistent development of each stage, then give the opportunity to practice / train until competence is achieved (automatism and high quality of execution). And only when competence is achieved, the application of clinical and practical skills on patients (this should be mandatory) is more interesting for students, since they understand and successfully perform all stages of the examination. Such training reduces the emotional stress and stress of students, limits the number of patients to achieve competence in performing the skill. This is especially important when there are not enough patients for practical training in the clinic.

The above training in clinical and practical skills is designed to allow students to take an active part in practical classes. At the same time, by systematizing the stages of learning in their classes, the teacher's skill and skill improves, and he also becomes competent in his field. Using our own pedagogical experience of working with students based on the application of systematized stages of training, we can assert that this model of mastering clinical/practical skills guarantees an increase in the effectiveness of training in practical classes.

Thus, modern student education requires a lot of attention to the presentation of the theory of medical diagnostic thinking. It is impossible to teach a student only the methods of studying a patient, it is impossible to make him remember those symptoms and syndromes that only correspond to a particular disease. It is necessary to train him to use the results of his methodical work correctly and consciously carry out the process of diagnostic thinking.

It should be noted that clinical thinking is a specific mental activity of a practical doctor, aimed at the most effective use of theoretical scientific knowledge, practical skills and personal experience in solving professional (diagnostic, therapeutic, prognostic and preventive) tasks to preserve the health of a particular patient. Since the process of processing the information received is part of the mental activity of the doctor, it often seems incomprehensible and even mystical to the student. Moreover, experienced doctors think so quickly and without strain that sometimes they themselves find it difficult to explain the logic of their thoughts. At the same time, each of them has its own style of thinking. Nevertheless, clinical thinking is based on certain principles, and their observance will help students and future doctors to make the analysis of information about the patient constructive and purposeful.

Botkin S.P. in the preface to the "Clinical Lectures" wrote that he was guided by "the desire to inform his comrades in the vocation of the techniques of research and thinking" in order to "facilitate the first steps of a beginner in independent practice" [3]. Following the precept of an outstanding clinician, we raised the question of the thinking of a doctor and his upbringing.

Undoubtedly, the introduction of our proposed method of teaching clinical thinking into the educational program of graduate students and its control will eventually show its positive results.

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